

Modelling Transport Decarbonisation Pathways in Vietnam: Synergies and Trade-offs in Supporting the Energy Transition

Nuzulia Fajriningrum¹, Leonhard Hofbauer^{2,*}, Naomi Tan^{3,4}, Steve Pye²

¹ *Bartlett School of Environment, Energy and Resources, University College London, United Kingdom*

² *UCL Energy Institute, University College London, United Kingdom*

³ *Geography and Environment, Loughborough University, United Kingdom*

⁴ *Centre for Environmental Policy, Imperial College London, United Kingdom*

* *Corresponding author. Email address: leonhard.hofbauer.18@ucl.ac.uk*

Abstract

Transport is the second-largest energy using sector in Vietnam and is projected to have the highest energy and emissions growth in future years. This paper explores options for decarbonising Vietnam's transport sector using a mixed-methods approach, including qualitative scenario design and quantitative energy system modelling. Three strategies are explored - modal shifting, fuel switching, and improving fuel economy, alongside Vietnam's 8th Power Development Plan to identify alternative pathways to reduce transport emissions. Further scenarios are constructed to assess the wider implications of low-carbon mobility in fostering Vietnam's energy transition towards climate mitigation targets.

We find that improving fuel economy is the most efficient transport-focused pathway to decouple emission and energy demand from mobility growth, while modal shift is crucial for reducing traffic congestion and carbon dioxide emission. Fuel switching to electric vehicles must be undertaken in parallel with efforts to lower carbon intensity in power generation, to avoid the risk of indirect emissions. Combining all three transport decarbonisation strategies with higher renewables and a carbon tax can fulfil Vietnam's unconditional Nationally Determined Contributions target by 2030. While the co-benefits of carbon dioxide abatement and fuel import avoidance will improve Vietnam's energy security and environmental sustainability, the study suggests that the risks of trade-offs in land-use implications and rising future electricity costs must be considered to support a just and equitable energy transition in Vietnam.

Keywords: transport, decarbonisation, energy modelling, emission reduction, energy transition, OSeMOSYS

Highlights

- OSeMOSYS modelling and scenario analysis analyse various transport strategies' impact on decarbonising energy systems in Vietnam.
- Combining fuel economy improvement with modal shifting and fuel-switching strategies significantly reduces carbon dioxide emissions from the transport sector.
- Sector coupling electromobility and clean electricity in Vietnam's 8th Power Development Plan is crucial for achieving its NDC target by 2030.
- Assessing the risks of escalation in electricity prices and environmental impacts from biofuel production is necessary for advancing Vietnam's energy transition policy.

List of Abbreviations

ASI	Avoid-Shift-Improve
ASIF	Activity-Share-Intensity-Fuel
ASEAN	Association of Southeast Asian Nations
BAU	Business-as-Usual
bpd	barrel per day
CCG	Climate Compatible Growth
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
COP	Conference of the Parties
DEA	Danish Energy Agency
E2/3W	Electric two/three-wheelers
EFFECT	Energy Forecasting Framework and Emissions Consensus Tool
EREA	Electricity and Renewable Energy Authority in Viet Nam
ERIA	Economic Research Institute for ASEAN and East Asia
ESOM	Energy System Optimization Model
ETP	Energy Transition Partnership
ETS	Emission Trading Scheme
EV	Electric Vehicle
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GHG	Greenhouse gas
GtCO ₂ e	Gigatons of carbon dioxide equivalent
GW	Gigawatts
HDV	Heavy duty vehicles
HFO	Heavy fuel oil
HHI	Herfindahl–Hirschman index
I/O	Input/Output
IEA	International Energy Agency
IEVN	Institute of Energy Vietnam
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
JETP	Just Energy Transition Partnership
JICA	Japan International Cooperation Agency
kWh	kilowatt-hours
LDV	Light duty vehicles
LEAP	The Long-Range Energy Alternatives Planning
LFO	Light fuel oil
MJ	Megajoules
MONRE	Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment
MOIT	Ministry of Industry and Trade
MOT	Ministry of Transport
MtCO ₂ e	Million [metric] tons of carbon dioxide equivalent
MTOE	Million [metric] tons of oil equivalent
NAMA	Nationally Appropriate Mitigation Actions
NDC	Nationally Determined Contribution
ND-CP	Decree of the Government (<i>Vietnamese</i>)
NDC-TIA	NDC Transport Initiatives for Asia

NEMP	National Energy Master Plan Vietnam
NO _x	Nitrogen Oxides
NZE	Net-Zero Emission
OSeMOSYS	Open-Source energy MOdelling SYStem
PJ	Petajoules
pkm	passenger-kilometre
PDP 8	8 th Power Development Plan Vietnam
PV	Photovoltaics
QD-TTg	Decision of the Prime Minister (<i>Vietnamese</i>)
RE	Renewable Energy
REA	Rapid Evidence Assessment
RES	Reference Energy System
RON	Research Octane Number
SO _x	Sulphur Oxides
tCO ₂ e	tons of carbon dioxide equivalent
TIMES	The Integrated MARKAL-EFOM System
tkm	tonne-kilometre
USD	United States Dollar
USDA	United States Department of Agriculture
VITRANSS	Vietnam National Transport Strategy Study
VND	Vietnamese Dong
VRE	Variable Renewable Energy

1. Introduction

Accelerating deep decarbonisation is imperative for achieving a net-zero emissions future. Global transport emissions have rebounded to 8 gigatons of carbon dioxide equivalent (GtCO₂e) following the easing of post-pandemic restrictions and need to immediately decrease by 3% per year to limit the average global temperature rise to below the 1.5°C scenario by 2030 [1,2].

Transportation is a key driver for development but its reliance on fossil fuels has meant the sector has also been a driver of carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions. Assessing how to decouple economic growth from transport emissions has become a priority for the Global South nations [3,4]. In these emerging economies, the diversity of policy options and the heterogeneity of transport systems and infrastructure make it challenging to pinpoint cost-effective policies and key technologies for decarbonisation, particularly for a country with high climate vulnerability like Vietnam [4–6]. Transitioning to low-carbon mobility in Vietnam requires balancing priorities between maintaining energy security, developing the economy, and protecting the climate and environment [7].

As the third recipient of the Just Energy Transition Partnership (JETP)¹ [8], Vietnam is currently in a strategic position to determine how financial and technical assistance can be mobilised for the transport sector. This sector is Vietnam's second-largest energy user, constituting 21% of its final energy and 18% of the country's emissions, with the highest projected growth over the next 30 years [9–11]. Decarbonising transport offers potential co-benefits, addressing concerns of traffic congestion and air pollution in addition to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions [12,13]. These externalities are estimated to add a 5% loss in national income due to the adverse impacts on productivity and health on top of the 3% reduction from climate-induced damages [14,15]. Therefore, Vietnam's government is committed to accelerating the low-carbon transition of transportation [16,17].

Following its Net-Zero by 2050 commitment, the country updated its Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) to pledge 15.8% unconditional emission mitigation by 2030 relative to 2022, 7% of which comes from the energy system, including transport [18]. Studies have modelled this decarbonisation pathway using a whole energy systems approach, but this method risks overlooking the specific features of the transport sector [19–21]. Meanwhile, transport-limited studies have been undertaken to better capture the detail of transport systems but provide limited insight on cross-sectoral implications [22,23].

Harmonising a transport decarbonisation strategy alongside the broader sustainable energy transition will be crucial due to Vietnam's current carbon-intensive energy supply (see Supplementary material A). Transitioning to electric vehicles (EV) without lowering carbon intensity in power generation develops risks of indirect emissions [24]. Comparably, switching to biofuel may raise the risk of environmental degradation due to increased land and water use [25]. Moreover, in 2023, Vietnam approved its Power Development Plan (PDP) 8² and National Energy Master Plan (NEMP)³, which have not been fully incorporated into prior studies and may offer substantial implications for Vietnam's transport decarbonisation.

This paper aims to explore Vietnam's alternative transport sector decarbonisation pathways in the context of the broader energy system transition. In particular, it addresses the following objectives:

¹ A financing mechanism from the International Partners Group (Japan, Canada, Denmark, France, Germany, Italy, Norway, the USA, the EU, and the UK) to the middle-income countries in supporting energy transition, launched at the 26th UN Climate Change Conference of the Parties (COP26).

² Prime Minister Decision No. 500/QĐ-TTg (2023).

³ Prime Minister Decision No. 893/QĐ-TTg (2023).

- Identify Vietnam's alternative transport decarbonisation pathways through quantitative modelling and qualitative scenario design and analysis.
- Analyse the implications of transport decarbonisation strategies on broader aspects of energy systems transition.
- Discuss the critical interactions between different elements and sectors in Vietnam's transport decarbonisation pathways.

The paper is structured as follows; Section 2 reviews the key literature on energy transition and transport decarbonisation, modelling and scenario analysis, and previous studies to identify the knowledge gaps and research questions. Section 3 elaborates on the research design and methodologies of the quantitative model selection and set-ups (including data and assumptions), qualitative scenario analysis. Section 4 then presents the results and analyses, with Section 5 discussing the key insights, reflecting on wider policy issues. Section 6 then concludes, identifying the study's contribution, and putting forward recommendations for potential avenues for future research.

2. Literature review

This literature review aims to analyse existing transport decarbonisation studies globally and in Vietnam and to identify gaps that this specific research aims to address. It also justifies and shapes the proposed approach to research.

2.1. Energy Modelling and Scenario Analysis

In resolving complex, systemic challenges like transport decarbonisation, one must first understand the nature of interactions between its system components [26]. It is particularly relevant in the case of developing countries, where implementing 'just' energy transition strategies involve balancing not only cross-sectoral and multi-level government priorities but also optimising short-term decision-making with long-term investment and system transformation [4,27]

The ability to provide an integrating framework to assess this system complexity is one of the prominent reasons why quantitative energy models have been gaining recognition for planning and policymaking in this field. They can help substantiate policy goals as the 'normative' or 'ideal' futures and generate different pathways to achieve them (backcasting) or explore how the particular decarbonisation policy may influence the future (exploratory) [28–30]. A review of 73 publications from 25 emerging countries in the Global South by Emodi *et al.* [6] demonstrates that quantitative modelling has increasingly been chosen to assess transport decarbonisation strategies, focusing on technology options and policy interventions. The functionality of a quantitative model primarily drives this trend, providing consistent frameworks to integrate cross-cutting issues and capture sectoral interactions in long-term energy transition pathways. While qualitative analyses like Bakker *et al.* [31], Arioli *et al.* [32] and ERIA [33] provide a detailed characterisation of complex transport strategies, it may be difficult to interpret how far each may decrease emissions. Therefore, Briand *et al.* [4] highlight the importance of combining the two methods, as it provides the opportunity for a deeper understanding of the qualitative storyline behind the transport decarbonisation measures while making the assumption explicit through quantifying parameters and assessing them through quantitative modelling tools.

In climate mitigation, Tager and Dikau [34] used qualitative scenarios to explore possible outcomes of decarbonisation measures whilst acknowledging the uncertainty of future system transformation. The paper shows the importance of having explicit narratives on top of quantitative modelling, which

strengthens the argument from Briand *et al.* [4] in employing the combined qualitative-quantitative analysis approach. Lefèvre *et al.* [35] pointed out that this mixed-method approach can be iterative. It may include qualitative participatory processes such as expert elicitations or secondary evidence reviews before undertaking the quantitative modelling. After that, qualitative analysis can translate the results into meaningful information for policymakers and facilitate further discussions. As seen in previous studies, combined qualitative-quantitative methods, along with transport-specific scenarios, successfully helped narrow down country-specific challenges of decarbonising the transport sector, particularly in the context of emerging economies [4,22].

2.2. Transport Modelling Studies in Vietnam

Emodi *et al.* [6] asserted that the uneven distribution of transport decarbonisation studies across the Global South might present a challenge for defining transport decarbonisation strategies in Vietnam, as the country was diagnosed with distinct gaps in scholarly literature. However, considerable publications have been made since, each with strengths and shortcomings.

From the perspective of Southeast Asia's regional-scale research [24,33] and multi-country studies [32], the issues of cross-sectoral governance has been an important feature of transport decarbonisation studies in Vietnam. These studies demonstrate the need to break down the siloed institutional approach and promote sector coupled analysis, particularly in modelling transport electrification and renewable electricity in Vietnam [4,24]. Other studies highlight that these developing nations show common traits of highly regulated petroleum fuel prices and electricity subsidies, which aggravate multi-dimensional challenges of decarbonisation when considering the broader energy trilemma: security, equity, and sustainability [36–38].

Recently, various national modelling efforts led by development agencies supporting government institutions have used commercial optimisation tools like TIMES or simulation models like PLEXOS [19,20,39,40], which are not open-source. Despite not explicitly focusing on transport, these models identify technology options for planning or investment purposes. In academic studies, the majority of models either assess the broader overall energy transition [41–44] or a narrower scope of single-measure transport interventions like modal shift [45], improved efficiency [41,46], or switching to biofuel or EVs [47–49].

A transport-focused scenario analysis from Oh *et al.* [22] assessed Vietnam's Transport Master Plan⁴ using a detailed bottom-up Avoid-Shift-Improve (ASI) approach. This was done through the EFFECT model soft-linked with a LEAP model to provide a whole system simulation, yielding a potential emission reduction of 14 MtCO₂e by 2030. Meanwhile, Thao *et al.* [23] summarised the potential reductions associated with different transport policy levers. They estimated total mitigation potential of 10-19 MtCO₂e abatement by 2030, based on updates to Vietnam's 2020 and 2022 NDCs. These studies demonstrate uncertainties for transport decarbonisation, particularly in electromobility (e-mobility) and intermodal shifting. Moreover, none of these studies incorporated the new PDP 8, NEMP, nor demonstrated the intended 37.5 MtCO₂e target for transport GHG emission reduction in the Government's Decree No. 6/ND-CP.

2.3. Knowledge gaps and research questions

Two key gaps are evident from this review. First, energy modelling efforts in Vietnam have yet to explicitly connect transport decarbonisation pathways with other sectors also in transition, notably the power sector. Most either conduct analysis at the broader energy system level, losing transport

⁴ A road map comprising different policies for infrastructure/network development including road (1454/QĐ-TTg), railway (1769/QĐ-TTg) and inland waterway (1829/QĐ-TTg) until 2030.

sector insights, or focused on transport-only mitigation efforts [22,23]. While EV and biofuel strategies have been studied for Vietnam, the broader trade-offs and synergies surrounding them have yet to be assessed explicitly. Second, studies to date have rarely adopted the mixed-methods approach of combining quantitative models with qualitative scenario design and analysis to better capture the complexity of transport emission reduction decisions in the Global South [4,6]. Assessments of other emerging nations exist, but not for the transport sector in Vietnam.

Based on these gaps, the following research questions are proposed: i) What are the alternative pathways to decarbonise the transport sector in Vietnam?; ii) What are the key implications of transport decarbonisation on wider energy systems transition?; iii) What critical synergies and trade-offs can be identified related to transport decarbonisation strategies in Vietnam that promote energy security, equity, and environmental sustainability?

3. Methodology

This research utilises a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative energy system modelling with qualitative scenario development and analysis methods. A Rapid Evidence Assessment (REA) was conducted to synthesise Vietnam-specific narrative scenarios of transport decarbonisation strategies from the literature (Section 2). Next, an Open-Source energy MOdelling SYStem (OSeMOSYS) model was developed to represent the transport sector and update the power sector, with scenarios modelled to identify and explore Vietnam's alternative transport decarbonisation pathways.

3.1. Model selection

Modelling provides a way to systematically assess long-term challenges and uncertainties around decarbonisation, in order to generate insights within specific scopes and boundaries [50–53]. A ‘bottom-up’ Energy System Optimisation Model (ESOM) is chosen to capture the optimal mix and technological details of Vietnam's transport and energy transformation until 2050 [54]. Unlike the ‘top-down’ macroeconomic model or I/O model, ESOMs can more easily provide feedback between emission constraints and necessary changes in transport technologies and systems [26,53,55].

OSeMOSYS is a free, open-source ESOM that fulfils exogenously defined demands in a least-cost, optimal solution considering specific objectives and system constraints [56]. The model has been used in prior studies in Vietnam [43,44] and other emerging countries for transport decarbonisation [57–59]. OSeMOSYS is also frequently used by international organisations and academic institutions in capacity-building events [60–62]. Despite its limitations - perfect foresight, data-intensive, and lack of macroeconomic feedback [63], the model provides valuable insights on alternative pathways comprising different transport emission reduction strategies in Vietnam. Complementing prior use of commercial modelling tools (TIMES, PLEXOS), this open-source study is beneficial as the models and data will be publicly available and replicable.

3.2. Model structure

The Reference Energy System (RES) illustrates the OSeMOSYS model's overall structure, where arrows indicate energy flows and boxes indicate technologies (see Supplementary material B). Figure 1 depicts a simplified RES for the transport sector.

Figure 1. Simplified RES for transport sector details in the OSeMOSYS model

Vietnam is modelled as a single aggregated region due to data availability. The analysis period is from 2021 to 2050, with 2020 as the base year and a social discount rate of 10% used [64]. The primary dataset was adapted from the Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) Vietnam Starter Data Kit [65], building on the previous model version [43] to develop new transport structures and update the power sector details. Other (residential, commercial, and industry) demands are kept as per the original analysis.

3.3. Model data and assumptions

Demand

Vietnam transport demands are defined separately as passenger (in passenger-km, or pkm) and freight (in tonne-km, or tkm) demand, each comprising roads, railways, and inland waterways [66]. Road transport activities are disaggregated using vehicle stock comparisons to represent the %-shares in the base year. Figure 2 represents a simple flow schematic for demand estimation outside of the model based on deriving transport energy service demands, while the annual energy consumption [67] is derived from the model.

Figure 2. Approach to transport energy service demand projection

The passenger transport demand is projected to grow in line with population, while freight follows manufacturing growth (1.99% and 2.23% annually, respectively) [66]. This rate of freight growth is conservative compared to previous studies [22,68] but is chosen so as to align proportionally with the Vietnam National Transport Strategy Study (VITRANSS) [69]. Bus demand combines all types of buses, car demand represents all types and sizes of cars, and motorcycle demand includes two/three-wheelers and mopeds [49,70]. The model does not include international aviation, maritime fleets, or active mobility (non-motorised) transport modes due to data availability and given the chosen boundary of the domestic CO₂ inventory. This simplified structure of transport demand is chosen to appropriately represent the essential elements of decarbonisation targets in Vietnam's policy [23,49,71]. Despite the flexibility to optimise the technology mix, it should be noted that the optimisation framework does not include endogenous mode choice between separate modal categories [72].

Technologies

With datasets for Vietnam-specific transport technology parameters being limited, this study relies on the techno-economic data from the VITRANSS study by JICA [69], Nationally Appropriate Mitigation Action (NAMA) documents, and NDC-Transport Initiative Asia (NDC-TIA) publications

[73,74], mainly focused on the road transport [68,75]. Details on the Vietnam railways are adapted from the JICA report [76]. As studies on larger road transport vehicles are limited, this work relies on approximated data from various modelling efforts and relevant publications [10,77–79]. Hence, refining Vietnam-specific heavy-duty vehicle data is crucial for future model versions.

OSeMOSYS provides flexibility for choosing vehicle technologies within each transport mode to fulfil the mobility demand, based on vehicle performance, cost and emissions. Choices between alternative vehicle technologies (e.g., electric or biofuel) consider the broad model objective of minimising costs and other policy limits e.g. emission limits or taxes [55,57]. The capital cost components are extracted from existing studies [69,73,74] with 2019 USD/VND currency exchange rate [80]. In addressing data gaps, approximation by Plazas-Niño *et al.* [81] is used (Equation 1).

$$\text{Transport Capital Costs} \left[\frac{\text{USD}}{\text{pkm or tkm}} \right] = \frac{\text{Unit technology cost [USD/v]}}{\text{Activities [km]} * \text{Occupancy factor [p or t/v]}} \quad (1)$$

Due to the absence of Vietnam-specific technology cost projections, this model takes conservative assumptions of constant capital costs except for EVs. Apart from fuel costs, all O&M costs are represented by fixed costs, which is assumed to be 3% of the annual capital cost for general modes and 2% for larger vehicles (buses, trucks, trains) [81]. Summaries of techno-economic assumptions can be found in Supplementary material C.

Fuels

This study further refines the model structure to disaggregate transport fuels, such as gasoline and diesel for the road and rail fleets, and fuel oil for ships. EV and biofuel vehicles are introduced as low-carbon alternatives in road and rail transport modes. Biofuel represents the E5 standard (5% ethanol and 95% gasoline) [82,83]. Resource restrictions on such fuels are set according to the production capacity of bio-ethanol plants in Vietnam [84]. Two refineries are characterised to represent the Dung Quat and Nghi Son refineries [85]. The costs of fuels are adapted from Vietnam Energy Statistics [9], including representations of biofuel subsidies, with similar projections as in Danish Energy Agency (DEA)'s report [86]. CO₂ emissions are linked to carbon content of fuel, similar to the Activity-Structure-Intensity-Fuel (ASIF) framework [68]. The factors are based on 2016 Vietnam's GHG Inventory [87], except for biofuel, approximated with combined ethanol-gasoline emissions factors. Biomass emissions are also included in the model, so they count under the emission constraints.

Power sector

Data assumptions for power sector technologies are based on Vietnam-specific dataset [88], including gradual cost improvements representing learning rates. The techno-economic details of power technologies are provided in Supplementary material C. Planned capacities have been revised based on the latest plan, PDP 8 [20] (Figure 3), which is integrated all the way out to 2050 as the minimum total annual capacity. Inter-annual variability of renewable generation is estimated using a single year of data (2016), aggregated into eight time-slices per year (four seasonal, two diurnal) to keep the model tractable. Electricity import capacity is adjusted based on PDP 8 [89] and NEMP [90], while transmission and distribution grid capacity are maintained from the previous model.

Figure 3. Power generation capacity projection based on Vietnam’s PDP 8

3.4. Scenario development

This study conducts a qualitative scenario design utilising the Rapid Evidence Assessment (REA) method [91,92] for interpreting and synthesising three strategies for transport decarbonisation in Vietnam. The review is based on a non-exhaustive range of secondary data from three databases with search terms, criteria, and final samples listed in Supplementary material E. Based on the evidence review, this study identifies three central strategies to reduce emissions from the Vietnam transport sector: **modal shifting (MS)**, **fuel switching (FS)**, and improving **fuel economy (FE)** or efficiency.

These strategies were layered individually and combined (**ALL**) on to the base PDP 8 reference scenario (**PDPL**) to compare the impact of transport decarbonisation strategies. A modified base PDP 8 scenario, **PDPH**, reflects a more optimistic outlook in respect of renewable generation roll out; hence, why combining **ALL+PDPH** is necessary to look for the maximum emission reduction potentials from coupling both transport and power sector decarbonisation efforts. Note that a **BAU** case is also considered, to provide an emissions trajectory in the absence of the PDP 8 implementation. Target-based scenarios (**NDC, JETP, NZE**) were also modelled to assess how whole-system optimised paths reach certain emission levels in the absence of specifically prescribed transport strategies.

Table 1 presents the range of scenarios considered with short narratives and assumed parameters.

Table 1. Scenarios focused on Vietnamese transport decarbonisation strategies

Code	Scenario	Narratives
No transport-specific decarbonisation strategy.		
PDPL	PDP 8 Low (<i>Reference</i>)	The PDP 8 is being implemented, following the lower limit of planned capacity installation (490 GW by 2050, 75% renewables). The power sector progressively shifts toward a more sustainable path, although the planned fossil generation remains (500/QD-TTg and 893/QD-TTg).

		No specific transport interventions are included.
PDPH	PDP 8 High	From PDPL, the international funds and partnerships enable the higher/upper limit of PDP 8 renewables capacity to be installed (573 GW by 2050, 80% renewables). No transport interventions are included.
BAU	Unconstrained future	The unconstrained scenario assesses the business-as-usual projection if the PDP 8 is not implemented, and only contracted power plants are maintained (67 GW by 2020). This scenario is not a reference and is exercised only to provide initial emission trends for comparison with decarbonisation cases.
Transport sector decarbonisation strategies (all other non-transport sectors are held constant).		
MS	Modal Shift (Strategy #1)	From PDPL, the public transport infrastructure development encourages passenger transport modality shifts. Cars and motorcycle use will decrease, while the rate of public transport will reach 20% of total activities by 2030. Meanwhile, 21.6% of the freight services from road transport will be shifted to the railway and inland waterway modes by 2030 (1658/QD-TTg).
FS	Fuel Switch (Strategy #2)	From PDPL, the rate of clean energy buses will reach 30% of total operating buses by 2030 (1658/QD-TTg). Electrification and green energy (E5 gasoline) are highly encouraged (888/QD-TTg), in total reaching 30-60% for both low and high-duty vehicles and 32-60% for two-wheelers between 2030-2050 (876/QD-TTg).
FE	Fuel Economy (Strategy #3)	From PDPL, the technology innovation in passenger vehicles improves fuel efficiency, gradually reducing up to 10% and 20% of the energy intensity by 2030 and 2050 (893/QD-TTg). This strategy also includes similar improvements in load factors in all freight transport modes.
ALL	All Strategies Combined	The government combines all three decarbonisation strategies (MS, FE, and FS with PDPL).
ALL+ PDPH	High Renewables Strategy	The government pushes for sector coupling between all combined transport decarbonisation strategies alongside higher renewable energy deployment in PDP 8 (2068/QD-TTg).
Target-based whole system decarbonisation (without the above specific transport strategies prescribed).		
NDC	Nationally Determined Contribution	Updated NDC (2022) unconditional target, which is 7% by 2030 from the entire energy sector emission. The conditional target of 24.4% is assumed to be achieved by 2050.
JETP	Just Energy Transition	JETP proposed plan [39,93]. The peak emission level and coal expansion will be reduced by 70 Mt and 6.8 GW, respectively, by 2030. Divestment in coal power plants is translated as an accelerated phase-out of 35% residual capacity, starting from 2035.
NZE	Net-Zero by 2050	Net-Zero target, where emission level from the energy sector is at 101 MtCO ₂ e by 2050 (893/QD-TTg).

(Note: QD-TTg: Vietnam's Prime Minister Decisions)

3.5. Sensitivity analysis

Considering the prominence of carbon pricing in Vietnam's emission mitigation [94–98], a sensitivity analysis is applied to the **ALL+PDPH** scenario to assess five different carbon tax levels (5, 20, 50, 75, and 100 USD/tCO₂e), approximated from the World Bank's (2023b) carbon price range and

implemented gradually from 2026 to match Vietnam's Emission Trading System (ETS) timeline [99,100]. The results are compared with the target-based scenarios (**NDC, JETP, NZE**) to see the impact of different tax levels in achieving decarbonisation targets.

As hydroelectricity generation is important for Vietnam, the drought in the Mekong River due to the El Nino phenomenon may dampen its decarbonisation efforts [101]. Moreover, the ambitious plan of the Dung Quat refinery capacity expansion and the third refinery establishment by 2031 might hinder the urgency of fuel transition [102]. On the other hand, PDP 8 encourages significant grid capacity expansion to support EV implementation. To observe how these issues may affect Vietnam's transport strategies, additional sensitivity analysis was performed, which include:

- *Drought*: reduction of water level in large hydropower reservoirs by 10-20% [103].
- *Refineries expansion*: 40 bpd by 2023, 70 bpd by 2031 [102].

4. Results

This chapter presents key findings of the modelling results in terms of how different pathways of transport decarbonisation strategies (MS, FE, FS) and their combination (ALL) in alignment with Vietnam's power sector advancement (PDPL/PDPH) may impact the country's energy demand (Subsection 4.1), electricity generation (Subsection 4.2), GHG emissions (Subsection 4.3), and costs and investments (Subsection 4.4). Target-based scenario results (NDC, JETP and NZE) are referred to as the 'cost-optimal' solution, with the sensitivity analysis on carbon tax presented to push the transport strategies further in reaching intended emission reduction targets. Additional sensitivities results are presented in brief to provide some additional insights on key issues noted in section 3.5 (Subsection 4.5).

4.1. Energy demand

In the reference scenario (PDPL), passenger transport final energy demand increases to 1,191 PJ by 2050, dominated by road transport. Figure 4 shows how the introduction of transport strategies: modal shifting (MS), fuel switching (FS), and fuel economy (FE) influence energy demand, and their combined impact (ALL). A key combined impact is the reduction in the total imported oil products by 371 MTOE (77%) by 2050 relative to PDPL. Alongside the capacity expansion, this alleviates 96% of total imports by 2050.

In MS, public vehicle (bus and train) activity reaches 30.9% of total passenger transport energy consumption by 2050. However, total demand remains at similar levels to PDPL due to low occupancy rates of buses [104]. In FS, overall demand is reduced by 14.5% by 2050 due to the higher efficiency of electric vehicles. The share of clean energy constitutes nearly half of total demand by 2050. Electricity demand for e-mobility is expected to grow significantly, by 7.3%/year to reach 191 PJ by 2050, over ten times the demand in 2020. Finally, in FE, improvements in fuel efficiency reduce energy demand by 27.2% across passenger transport demand by 2050, leading to an energy intensity improvement from 4.3 MJ/pkm (in PDPL) to 3.0 MJ/pkm by 2050, resulting in lower fuel imports. These results confirm that the Vietnam National Energy Efficiency Program (VNEEP) and the recent NEMP targets to improve efficiency by at least 15%-20% by 2050 are attainable [90,105].

Figure 4. Passenger transport demand profile in transport decarbonisation strategy scenarios

For the combination of all strategies (ALL), results indicate that Vietnam's National Green Growth Strategy (NGGS) target to increase the share of clean energy to 30% by 2045 is fulfilled [93]. Biofuel vehicles play an important role, benefitting alongside conventional ICE vehicles in fuel efficiency improvement. EVs do not feature as in a lower demand scenario because the lower cost biofuel can meet the required fuel switching levels [106], creating less strain on the grid.

Meanwhile, Figure 5 displays pathways where the model determines how to decarbonise transport to reach climate targets (NDC, JETP, and NZE), as opposed to prescribing a given transport strategy. Biofuel production is maximised in the short term due to lower capital investments. After reducing coal-based power generation, the model sees strong electrification of passenger fleets after 2040, indicating a synergy between e-mobility and increasing renewable power generation. This synergy is not observed in ALL due to the absence of an emission limit, which leads to the model prioritising biofuel as the more cost-optimal solution compared to the EVs.

Figure 5. Comparison of passenger transport demand profile in optimised scenarios (NDC, JETP, and NZE) with the combined transport decarbonisation scenario (ALL).

Figure 6 shows freight demand reaching 562 PJ by 2050 in the PDPL scenario, 77% of which is road-based. Shifting the logistical activities from trucks to railway and inland waterway modes under MS will reduce demand by 10% by 2050 due to the higher load factor per service unit [77]. FS and FE strategies see higher reductions of 20-40% in energy demand by 2050 achieved by switching to EVs and improving the efficiency or load factor, such as through the Green Freight Initiative pilot projects in Vietnam [78], aiming to optimise heavy-duty vehicles (HDV) capacities, particularly in cement and manufacturing fleets.

Figure 6. Freight transport demand profile in decarbonisation scenarios

Overall, freight energy intensity falls from 2.1 MJ/tkm (in PDPL) to around 1.9, 1.7 and 1.2 MJ/tkm in MS, FS, and FE respectively by 2050, indicating potential for the improvement in operational efficiency of Vietnam's transport logistics scheme. By combining these approaches in the ALL Scenario, both the intensity and total energy consumption reach half its initial level in the PDPL Scenario, in which 30% of final demand are replaced by alternative fuelled vehicles (biofuel and EV). Figure 7 contrasts model-determined approaches under decarbonisation targets, compared to transport-prescribed strategies. Strong electrification of road transport is observed, but only after 2035. The results do not include biofuel potentially due to constrained resources, leading to the model prioritising electrification of two-wheelers and light-duty vehicles (LDV) as the more cost-effective solution. Due to no intermodal competition between road and railway transport, the model chooses the most cost-effective option among road transport alternatives: electric trucks with higher efficiency.

Figure 7. Comparison of freight transport demand profile in optimised scenarios (NDC, JETP, and NZE) with the combined transport decarbonisation pathway (ALL)

4.2. Power generation and capacity

Two power generation capacity projections are constructed based on the PDP 8 document: the PDPL scenario (490 GW with 75% RE) as a reference and the PDPH scenario (573 GW with 80% RE) to represent higher renewables. All transport scenarios are exercised using the PDP 8 power generation profile and represented by the PDPL in this subsection. Figure 8 demonstrates that the PDPL scenario aligns with NDC and JETP in 2050, while PDPH shows the importance of integrating a more ambitious renewable energy capacity expansion to reach the NZE requirement. In addition, NDC, JETP and NZE all see divestment away from coal and gas power plants. These scenarios only utilise existing capacity, contrasting with the planned coal expansion in PDP 8 between 2021-2030 which could hamper Vietnam’s ability to meet climate goals, and make the route to transport decarbonisation via EVs problematic, as seen in China and Lithuania [104].

Figure 8. Total annual installed power plant capacity in PDPL and PDPH scenarios, compared to the NDC, JETP and NZE decarbonisation scenarios

The power generation profile in Figure 9 confirms that dammed hydro will play a prominent role for Vietnam's low-carbon electricity [44], balancing the grid when solar or wind generation is low. The increase in electricity generation in the NZE scenario by 2050 is due to the need to fully electrify the transport sector by 2045, along with improved electrification and efficient appliances in other sectors.

Figure 9. Total annual power generation in PDPL and PDPH scenarios compared to the NDC, JETP and NZE decarbonisation scenarios

4.3. Emissions

To assess the emissions from different scenarios, these are compared to the BAU scenario which illustrates a high emission trajectory if the PDP 8 was not implemented. Figure 10 demonstrates that implementing the power sector mitigation plan through the PDP 8, as in PDPL (reference), already abates a large share of emissions by promoting renewables. It indicates that the PDP 8 can help to reduce emissions by up to 70 MtCO₂ by 2030. Then, compared to this reference, different scenarios highlight how transport decarbonisation strategies may contribute to reducing the overall emission even further.

Annual Vietnam Energy Sector CO₂ Emission

Figure 10. Projected annual energy system emission in the modelled scenarios

Individually, FE is the most effective lever to reduce emissions compared to FS and MS due to the higher reduction in transport demand. In this scenario, increasing fuel efficiency by 20% by 2050 decreases the emission level by 3.6% of the remaining emission in 2030 after the PDP 8 implementation (in PDPL). Combining all decarbonisation strategies (ALL) will reduce emissions by

4.3%, or 16.3 MtCO₂ by 2030, while implementing higher renewable power generation (ALL+PDPH) increases reduction to 6.3% (23.7 MtCO₂).

The above decarbonisation strategies were focused on the transport sector. In Figure 10, the gradual rise in emission beyond 2035 indicates how the unabated emission from other sectoral demands offset the emissions reduction from greening the transportation, particularly from residual coal and biomass needed for industrial thermal heating (see Supplementary material D), highlighting the need for a whole system approach. It should be noted that CO₂ emissions from bioenergy combustions are included in this study, counter to other studies that omit biomass carbon accounting from non-land-use sectors due to assumptions of carbon-neutrality [1]. The comparison of potential emission abatement can be seen in Figure 11, with ALL+PDPH (transport and power sector only) nearly meeting the unconditional NDC target for the whole energy sector (7%) by 2030.

Figure 11. Potential annual CO₂ emission abatement by 2030 and 2050 from each transport strategy scenario compared to the reference scenario (PDPL)

We also considered how broader climate targets could be met for the whole energy system (as considered in NDC, JETP and NZE) by incrementally adding higher carbon taxes on to the transport decarbonisation cases (in Figure 10). Figure 12 shows that a 5 USD/tCO₂e carbon tax level will help the energy system reach the unconditional NDC target of 7% CO₂ reduction by 2030. A progressive, higher level of carbon tax between 75-100 USD/tCO₂e is necessary to close the emission gap to JETP (blue dashed line), which may be interpreted as higher environmental protection taxes [107]. No carbon tax level deployed meets the NZE target, illustrating the critical need to decarbonise other sectors beyond transport and power.

Figure 12. The cumulative trend of CO₂ emission abatement in the modelled scenarios compared to the unconstrained future (BAU) if the power and transport measures are not implemented.

4.4 Costs and investments

The estimated cumulative capital investment needed to implement Vietnam's PDP 8 is 114 billion USD until 2030 and 391-504 billion USD (PDPL-PDPH) until 2050. (Figure 13). This model results align with the estimated figure of investments in the official PDP 8 document (500/QD-TTg), which is 119 billion USD for the 2021-2030 period and around 364-511 billion USD for 2031-2050.

Figure 13. Total cumulative capital investments for implementing PDP 8 (with higher/PDPH and lower/PDPL renewable capacity) in 5-year timeframes.

Figure 14 illustrates how power system capacity expansion in pursuing PDP 8 affects long-term electricity production costs. It indicates that the actual tariff of Vietnam, which was around 1,920

VND or around 8.2 cents per kWh in May 2023 [108], is slightly below the modelled electricity production cost of 9.0 cents per kWh. The model resembles Vietnam's current power production cost data from EVN and MOIT, which is around 2,036 VND or 8.7 cents per kWh. The massive capital investments will cause a rise in overall generation cost, which is expected to reach 0.22 USD/kWh by 2050, nearly reaching current level of Singapore's electricity cost [109], which is currently one of the highest unsubsidised price points in Asia due to a lack of domestic resources (95% from imported natural gas). Figure 15 implies that PDPL has a slightly higher cumulative capital costs in the power system compared to NDC and JETP due to the different preferences toward ongoing coal projects. Meanwhile, much higher investments are expected for achieving the net-zero future (NZE), far beyond the upper limit of RE investments stated in PDPH.

Figure 14. Projected trend of Vietnam's average electricity generation costs up to 2050

Figure 15. Projected total cumulative Vietnam's cumulative power system costs up to 2050

4.5 Additional sensitivity analysis results

Technical constraints representing drought on the combined transport scenario (ALL) confirms that lower reservoir levels may decrease hydroelectricity output by 5%-15% through the modelling period. The model mitigates this by bringing online an additional 20% coal and 10% biomass power, which undo the effects of decarbonisation measures and lead to 1.6 MtCO₂ higher emissions in 2030. Meanwhile, combining all three low-carbon transport strategies (ALL) with further refinery capacity expansions will significantly reduce fuel import dependency, with the share of domestically sourced fuels increasing from 77% up to 96% by 2050 (see Supplementary material D).

5. Discussion

This section discusses key implications of the results regarding synergies and trade-offs across the alternative transport decarbonisation pathways in supporting Vietnam's energy transition, with consideration of the energy trilemma dimensions (security, equity *and* environmental sustainability).

5.1 Trade-offs: energy and water security

In the combined decarbonisation strategies scenario (ALL), biofuel for transport energy consumption reaches nearly 60% of its assumed maximum resources of 637.5 PJ by 2050. As the model constraint is set at approximately 70% of IRENA's [110] estimated residue potentials, there is a possibility that the biofuel availability for gasohol (gasoline-ethanol) and biodiesel could be further expanded. For example, the feasibility of 10%-v/v (E10/B10) mixture to encourage further decarbonisation could be assessed. The cost-competitiveness of biofuel can be seen from all target-based scenarios, which maximise its production (NDC, JETP and NZE). However, this result is subject to biofuel price uncertainty, which in this model is set at 5% below RON95 gasoline to reflect subsidies and Vietnam's lower ethanol import tariff [111].

With estimation of global average efficiency of lignocellulosic processes (40%) and biofuel yield (150 GJ/hectare), combined with the remaining bioenergy demand from the other (non-transport) sectors in the ALL scenario, the model estimates a total need of the amount of produced sugar-based crops residue from 5.6 million hectares of land [110]. This means that by 2050, total bioenergy production would require agricultural waste or residue produced from 80% of the total arable land in Vietnam (6.7 million hectares in 2020, assuming no further liberation or degradation[112]), with the potential area of cultivation concentrated around the Red River delta and Mekong River delta.

This presents other issues since the hydropower generation in Vietnam, including the imported electricity from Laos, depends on the state of the water reservoir in the Mekong River. Tuan *et al.* [113] stated that 1 L ethanol production requires massive irrigation, around 30 litres (L) of water. With regards to Vietnam's existing 197 million L/year bioethanol operational capacity [84], water requirements might reach 5.9 billion L/year for substituting only 5% of gasoline. Moreover, the location of arable land in the river deltas makes it susceptible to the changes in flow and sediment levels. In consideration of environmental concerns and uncertainties associated with Vietnam's first-generation biofuel from feedstock plantations, several studies prefer more conservative bioenergy assumptions [83,84,114].

Moreover, a further exercise of the impact of drought (Supplementary material D) demonstrates how water security strongly impacts the mitigation efforts due to Vietnam's high dependency on hydropower, presenting risks of retreat to coal power in case of shortages [17]. Therefore, implementing a fuel-switching strategy requires a thorough assessment of the climate-water-energy-land nexus to consider trade-offs between clean energy (biofuel or hydropower for supporting e-mobility), food, and water security [115] that will impact the welfare of Vietnamese rural and coastal communities.

5.2 Synergies: e-mobility and clean electricity

Concerning a switch to e-mobility, the ALL scenario assumes a relatively modest EV penetration, given that PDP 8 assumes low-level projection of transport electrification [20] and low bi-directional EV charging technology readiness. However, results indicate that by integrating EV promotion with renewable energy in the power sector (ALL+PDPH) and grid expansion, higher levels of emission reduction can be achieved, particularly after 2030, due to the system's ability for a more ambitious expansion of VRE like wind and solar PV at scale.

This synergy is widely endorsed by most of the Vietnam-specific studies [43,116,117] and other developing countries [4], demonstrating the positive feedback from integrating EV technologies as anchor demands to stabilise the grid and accommodate peak VRE generation. Results from the target-based scenarios confirm that electrification of transport is vital for future low-carbon mobility but is only preferred after significantly reducing grid carbon intensity through reduced coal and gas power generation.

Despite the multiple benefits of both more efficient energy and lower emissions, EV implementation is prone to institutional resistance (carbon lock-in) due to high investments and 'radical' changes in infrastructure [114,118]. There is also a risk of a rebound because the efficiency gains may be offset by increased mobility, causing a rise in overall energy consumption [119].

5.3 Trade-offs: affordable energy for all

In all target-based scenarios, electrification is prioritised for personal vehicles like cars and electric two/three-wheelers (E2/3W). This is potentially due to the assumption that public fleets electrification is considered too expensive, indicating the model's limitation that requires intensive cost data and trajectory, assuming perfect foresight. It also underlined the importance of keeping public EV prices affordable to stimulate demand.

The role of E2/3W in prior studies is contested, as it has high potential [70,120] but is hard to upscale due to market saturation [121]. Despite potentially reducing 40% of fuel-based local air pollution, E2/3W and electric LDVs may not be beneficial for resolving Vietnam's severe congestion in major cities [122]. Therefore, modal shifting is necessary, considering public transport might be more accessible for the government to regulate and finance instead of relying on personal EV purchases.

Another consideration is the risk of rising electricity generation costs. Implementing PDP 8 might substantially elevate the competitive electricity production cost after 2030, leading to the risk of cost pass-through to consumers, which may lead to fuel poverty [123]. This trade-off between paying less fuel and more for EV investment and electricity prices will determine people's travel behaviour at the micro level. At the macro scale, despite the estimated USD 980 million 'green' revenues from 77% fuel import avoidance in the ALL scenario, switching to clean mobility may lead to an upsurge in electricity imports, as seen in the last year of the NZE scenario [114].

5.4 Trade-offs: secure or sustainable supply?

Assuming an average gasoline emission factor of 2.3 kgCO₂/L [124], the high carbon tax level (75-100 USD/tCO₂e) to achieve the JETP target can be translated as 4,100-5,300 VND/L environmental protection tax, which is only 30-70% higher than the existing tax rate for gasoline (3,000 VND/L) [125]. However, Vietnam's Minister of Finance later imposed a tax reduction on petrol importation to reduce gasoline costs and improve supply security and equity amidst the worldwide energy crisis and inflation [102,107]. This decision reflects the constant 'trilemma' faced by emerging economies, meaning that integrating higher tax levels as considered in the model might be counter-intuitive, particularly considering the possible pass-through to the price of energy commodities for society.

Despite not being fully considered in this model version, Vietnam's NEMP (893/QD-TTg) incorporates significant measures to improve its energy security, including increasing oil and petroleum production [126]. While the decision may improve energy security and equity, it would bring a further challenge of carbon lock-in that hinders the progress of clean energy alternatives in the transport sector, compromising emission reduction. NEMP also earmarks coal imports for power plant supply to encourage mining and power production, which might dampen the significance of transport decarbonisation. Considering the increase in the country's statistical measure of market

concentration represented by the Herfindahl–Hirschman Index (HHI) [9], there is an immediate need for Vietnam to improve its supply diversification, particularly from sustainable resources.

5.5. Uncertainties and limitations

As the study focuses on transport sector decarbonisation, it omits details from other sectors (residential, industrial and commercial), which may prove significant in reducing overall emissions to reach the climate targets. In addition, the emission analysis is linked to fuel consumption instead of specific emission per vehicle technologies and only includes CO₂, which made the local air pollution analysis incomplete. Expanding the scope to methane (CH₄) and other emission gases (NO_x and SO_x), would increase the breadth of insight from this study, potentially incorporating further measures related to the strategic policy documents like the Action Plan for Methane Emissions Reduction⁵ and the National Action Plan on Air Quality Management⁶ [127–129].

The model represents Vietnam's transport system in a simplified structure and aims to offer insights instead of actual future predictions [130]. The demand projection for transport is assumed to be linked to the trajectory of population and GDP in manufacturing growth, which is relatively low compared to prior studies and includes high uncertainty resulting from the post-pandemic recovery [131]. The model also incorporates assumptions about future fuel prices, with substantial uncertainties in biofuel prices considering limited domestic production and resource availability [83,132]. Further exercises representing a wider range based on Vietnam's published policies like National Master Plan 2021-2030 or Roadmap of Biofuel Blending⁷ would be useful, as would further primary data collection and expert elicitations as complementary methods.

Assumptions for large vehicles' learning rates, energy intensity and efficiency were aggregated from extensive sources and prior studies but are not entirely Vietnam-specific [133]. Hence, the development of a Vietnam-specific transport technology catalogue and macroeconomic models to refine the shortcomings in large-vehicle technology details and mobility growth projections would be useful future additions. Active mobility is not accounted for and may be essential for Vietnam's future urban passenger transport [134]. International shipping and aviation are also not included due to the complexity of cross-border regulations and policy agreements [135].

Despite being simplified, the structure of this model does capture the critical parameters from the stated policies or intended targets related to Vietnam's energy transition [23]. Moreover, for financial representation, the model investment figures substantiate the number in the PDP 8 [89] and the price of current electricity generation [108], which makes it possible to align the results with the broader energy systems transition. Incorporating other models like FlexTool and FINPLAN can further provide analysis on how these decarbonisation strategies affect flexibility and finances of the power sector projects, underpinning advanced financial planning and political decisions [136].

6. Conclusions

This research concludes that exploring different pathways and analysing synergies and trade-offs in decarbonising the transport sector is crucial in supporting Vietnam's energy transition to ensure the balance between providing secure, affordable, and sustainable energy for society.

⁵ Prime Minister Decision No. 942/QĐ-TTg (2022).

⁶ Prime Minister Decision No. 1973/QĐ-TTg (2021).

⁷ Prime Minister Decision No. 53/QĐ-TTg (2012).

In addressing the first research question, various decarbonisation scenarios have been identified and explored through a combined quantitative-qualitative method. This has produced alternative pathways for transport sector decarbonisation in Vietnam represented by the ALL Scenario, which manages to reach 16.3 MtCO₂ (4.3%) of emissions reduction by 2030 through combined transport strategies. Integrating the higher renewable energy penetration in PDP 8 increases this to 23.7 MtCO₂ (6.3%), whilst an additional carbon tax of 5 USD/tCO₂e from 2026 is needed to meet the NDC target by 2030 (7%). Raising these carbon tax levels may be necessary to encourage JETP implementation, while NZE targets can only be attained by decarbonisation of other sectors in addition to transport.

The modelling results are analysed to assess the implications of transport decarbonisation strategies on energy system demand and emission, costs, and investments, as related to the second research question about its key implications on wider system transition. Of all the transport strategies, the most effective measure is improving fuel efficiency, as it reduces a significant amount of GHG emissions. Fuel switching must be implemented in synergy with renewable electricity generation, as it risks shifting the transport emissions to the power sector if significant coal generation remains in the mix. The NDC, JETP, and NZE scenarios confirm these findings by optimising biofuel usage instead of fleet electrification in the short term. The model progressively reduces fossil-based power generation before massively deploying EVs from 2040 onwards. While only reducing smaller percentages of emissions, modal shifting would likely create co-benefits of reduced traffic congestion and local air pollution, which could only be captured partially in this study due to the limitation on representing active travel and intermodal competition. The total investment needed in green vehicles is estimated to reach USD 15.1 billion, about 13% of the estimated power sector investment in the first phase of PDP 8 until 2030. Considering these financial implications, the modal shifting strategy could present a quick win to optimise existing public transport infrastructure.

In answering the final question, the study concludes that various critical synergies and trade-offs can be perceived between different elements in transport decarbonisation. By combining all transport decarbonisation strategies, up to 0.95 GtCO₂ net cumulative total system emission reductions can be achieved along with co-benefits of declining local air pollution and cumulative savings of 371 MTOE of avoided fuel imports to 2050, significantly improving Vietnam's energy security and environmental sustainability. Despite the strong synergy of e-mobility with renewables, there are potential trade-offs in the equity dimension, as the long-term electricity cost may rise due to high capital investments needed to provide low-carbon electricity for EVs, in addition to the degradation of land and water security from upscaling biofuel productions.

With consideration of the model's limitation in representing the actual demand due to aggregated data and uncertainties in future fuel prices, technology innovation, and policy developments, the study contributes to the scholarly literature by providing novel insights on transport decarbonisation through intersectoral assessments of transport-power strategies by incorporating PDP 8 and JETP targets as recent highlights in Vietnam's energy transition. The findings may be helpful to inform future researchers in Vietnam's academic and government institutions in substantiating the possible synergies and trade-offs surrounding transport decarbonisation.

While this study improves the understanding of Vietnam's transport decarbonisation, diverse research areas remain to be explored. This study suggests developing a climate-land-energy-water system (CLEWs) nexus research to assess biofuel and biomass sustainability. Future modelling works could usefully consider incorporating active mobility or expanding the strategies to account for advanced technologies like bi-directional EV chargers, hydrogen, or sustainable fuels for international maritime and aviation, complementing the current scope of the transport technology representation.

While Vietnam's recent transport and power sector policies are well-aligned with climate targets, this study recommends divesting from the coal power expansion in the PDP 8 before massively implementing EVs to prevent further emission and keep the electricity generation cost affordable. Moreover, future policy decisions in Vietnam should consider the balance between short-term energy security and long-term climate targets, as currently, many trade-offs would have to be made in decarbonising transport despite the significant co-benefits for the energy system, economy, and environment.

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Authorship contribution statement

Nuzulia Fajriningrum: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Visualization. **Leonhard Hofbauer:** Writing – review & editing. **Naomi Tan:** Data curation, Writing – review & editing. **Steve Pye:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Writing – review & editing, Project administration.

Data availability

Data and model files can be assessed at: <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11393373>

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